

CONGENITAL MALFORMATIONS :RELEVANCE AND EPIDEMIOLOGY IN THE BUKHARA REGION

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to study the morphological features of pediatric autopsy associated with malformations. The analysis of pediatric autopsy was carried out on the basis of official accounting and reporting documentation of the Bukhara Regional Pathology Bureau for 2014-2015. During the study period, 203 autopsy cases were performed.

Introduction. Autopsy - (from the Greek. Autopsia - seeing with your own eyes) autopsy of the dead. It is an integral method of the pathological service. The autopsy method makes it possible to study the stages of development of many diseases. Organs and tissues taken at autopsy are examined using macroscopic and microscopic research methods. An autopsy confirms the correctness of the clinical diagnosis or reveals a diagnostic error, establishes the causes of death of the patient, features of the course of the disease, reveals the effectiveness of the use of medications, diagnostic manipulations, develops statistics of mortality and mortality, etc. When a child is born, this is the most wonderful moment in our entire life! A child who has given birth with a healthy is the wealth of the family, the health care system and the state!

Relevance: Malformations are developmental anomalies, a set of

deviations from the normal structure of the body that occur during intrauterine or, less often, postpartum development. Congenital malformations of the fetus (CM) are one of the most dangerous complications of pregnancy, which comes first among the causes leading to childhood disability and mortality. The birth of a child with congenital developmental defects always overwhelms the family, this topic is one of the most difficult. At the first moment, the spouses experience an incomparable psychological shock, which then turns into a feeling of guilt, it seems to them that they will never have a healthy child. Congenital malformations of the fetus (CMF) are one of the most threatening complications of pregnancy, which comes first among the causes leading to childhood disability and mortality. Statistics are frightening: against the background of decreasing child mortality, an increase in the number of congenital malformations is observed in most countries of the world. According to

long-term statistics, around the world, about 5% of children are born with congenital diseases. CMs are the cause of approximately 20% of deaths in the neonatal period, and also occupy a significant place in the practice of obstetrics and gynecology, medical genetics of pediatric surgery and orthopedics, and pathological anatomy. It is estimated that about 1 in 33 newborn babies have congenital malformations, and about 3.2 million babies each year have some form of developmental disability. An estimated 270,000 children die each year from malformations during the first 28 days of life.

The term "congenital anomalies" or "congenital malformations" refers to any congenital functional or structural abnormality that occurs in the fetus and newborn. Malformations may appear in later periods. Depending on the etiology, hereditary (genetic), exogenous and multifactorial congenital malformations of the fetus are distinguished in the form of embryonic dysmorphogenesis, or chromosomal and genomic mutations (chromosomal diseases).

Multifactorial means malformations resulting from the combined effects of genetic and exogenous factors. Genetically determined forms (gene and chromosomal) account for about 25-30%, exogenous (teratogenic) - 2-5%, multifactorial - 30-40%, forms of unclear etiology - 25-50% of cases of congenital malformations. The most common chromosomal abnormalities: Down syndrome (trisomy 21), Patau syndrome (trisomy 13), Edwards syndrome (trisomy 18), Turner syndrome (monosomia 45X0).

The most common congenital fetal malformations are:

- complete or partial absence, deformation of one or another organ or part of the body (limbs, brain, internal organs);
- anatomical defects of the face and neck (clefts of the upper lip and palate, other anomalies of the facial skeleton);
- malformations of the central nervous system: anencephaly, hydrocephalus, spina bifi da;
- congenital heart defects;
- congenital malformations of the gastrointestinal tract;
- anomalies in the development of the kidneys, adrenal glands, bladder.

The aim of the study is to study the morphological features of pediatric autopsies associated with developmental defects.

Methods: The analysis of pediatric autopsies was carried out on the basis of the official accounting and reporting documentation of the Bukhara regional pathoanatomical bureau for 2014-2015. During the study period, 203 autopsies were performed.

Results of the study: When assessing congenital malformations, it turned out that 24% (6 cases) had multiple malformations (microcephalus, hydrocephalus, renal agenesis, pulmonary hypoplasia, absence of one lung, clubfoot of the lower extremities, stenosis, intestinal atresia, multilobular spleen, monocotyledonous liver, cryptorchidism, hypoplasia of the lower jaw, cleft palate (cleft palate), cleft lip (cleft

lip), polydactyly, syndactyly, etc.); 20% (5 cases) revealed a congenital malformation of the cardiovascular system (defect of the interventricular septum, three-chambered heart with one common ventricle (vestigial right ventricle),

Tetralogy of Fallot, mitral valve atresia, anomaly of large veins - anomaly of

drainage-inflow of pulmonary veins into the right atrium, stenosing pulmonary trunk); 16% (4 cases) were found to have a congenital malformation of the gastrointestinal tract (atresia, malrotation, intestinal stenosis). Among the congenital malformations, other malformations have also been identified. (Fig 2).

Rice. 2.

Morphological analysis of congenital malformation.

Note:

- 1- multiple congenital malformations.
- 2- congenital malformation of the cardiovascular system.
- 3- congenital malformation of the gastrointestinal tract.
- 4- congenital brain defect.
- 5- congenital malformation of the biliary tract.

6- congenital lung disease.

7- congenital hernia of the esophageal opening of the diaphragm.

8- congenital malformation of the maxillofacial region

Conclusion: it is necessary to continue at the regional level medical and organizational measures aimed at early diagnosis of congenital developmental anomalies in order to make a timely prognosis for the life and health of the mother and fetus.

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